

The Perceptual Learning Styles and Teaching Styles in Araling Panlipunan of Selected Public Secondary Schools: An Input for the Development of Teaching Pedagogies

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ABSTRACT: This study investigates the relationship between the teaching styles of Araling Panlipunan teachers and the perceptual learning styles of students in selected public secondary schools. Employing a descriptive research design, the study involved 353 Grade 8 students and 31 Araling Panlipunan teachers from three secondary schools in the Division of Valenzuela City, selected through purposive sampling. Data were collected using an adapted and validated survey questionnaire, which demonstrated excellent reliability (Cronbach's $\alpha = 0.967$). Results indicate a notable mismatch between teachers' teaching styles and students' preferred learning styles. Most students exhibited auditory and visual learning preferences and favored individual learning approaches, whereas teachers predominantly employed kinesthetic and tactile styles, emphasizing group-based activities. This misalignment suggests that instructional effectiveness may be enhanced by aligning teaching methods with students' perceptual learning preferences. The findings underscore the importance of teacher awareness and adaptability in instructional planning. Enhancing teachers' understanding of learners' perceptual styles can inform the development of responsive and effective pedagogical practices in Araling Panlipunan instruction.

KEYWORDS: Auditory Learning Style; Visual Learning Style; Kinesthetic Learning Style; Tactile Learning Style; Perceptual Learning Styles; Teaching Styles

1.0 INTRODUCTION

The concepts of perceptual learning styles and teaching styles have been extensively discussed in the field of education for the past two decades. Researchers recognize that students learn in different ways and in the same manner, and teachers have varying methodologies and strategies. Perceptual learning style is observed to be consistent across settings and tasks has been considered as one of the influential factors in students' learning. Also, the instructional approaches of teachers are just as diverse as their students, which affects educational outcomes. Matching teaching and learning styles improved students' achievement (Hou 2007). Aligning the learning styles of students with teaching styles could lead to an improvement in academic achievement (Zeeb's 2004). Zeeb used the information obtained from assessing learning and teaching styles to help teachers modify their teaching styles to accommodate varying learning preferences, which resulted in improving students' test scores.

The narrower the gap between teacher intention and learner interpretation, has greater the chances of achieving the desired learning outcome (Kumaravadivelu, 1991). This mismatch results in an ineffective learning process in the classroom (Craspo & Hayen, 2006). The manner in which a learner characteristically gets, holds onto, and recalls information is collectively coined as the individual's perceptual learning style. A student may learn best by seeing, hearing, being active, or reflecting, to name a few. Perceptual learning styles are typically described by a student's sensory modalities (i.e., visual, tactile, auditory, and kinesthetic) and intellectual processes (i.e., active, reflective, global, or analytical). On the one hand, teaching style, as defined by the existing literature, refers to the approach of teachers put into practice to carry out teaching and learning activities. This typically includes giving lectures, demonstrating, facilitating, and holding discussions or role-playing.

The K-12 Araling Panlipunan curriculum aims to develop students' 21st Century Skills to nourish a functionally literate and develop a nationalistic Filipino. It provides opportunities for students to become citizens who are investigative, critical thinkers, responsible, productive, environmentally friendly, patriotic, and values-oriented. In order to provide effective learning in the current Social Studies curriculum, the learning environment should promote ways of addressing individual differences and provide avenues for active participation. When students' learning styles are matched with appropriate approaches in teaching, their motivation, performance, and achievement will increase, as well as be enhanced (Brown, 1994). Learner achievement affects their academic

placement in enrichment or remediation programs while in school and also affects their acceptance or rejection by the institution of higher learning.

This study of perceptual learning styles is timely, as individual learners vary considerably in how they learn. Any given person has academic or learning strengths that are determined by a combination of hereditary and environmental influences. These strengths, which translate into preferences to learn and communicate visually, spatially, and tactilely, are one's learning style, thereby bringing forth a revitalized interest that is found relevant. This study, therefore, is a basis for crafting teaching pedagogies that are deemed fit to the needs of Araling Panlipunan learners, hence this study.

The researcher has been a teacher of Grade 7 and 8 Araling Panlipunan for five years. When she first entered the school, it was glaring that students' compositions were so diverse and consequently subject teachers had difficulty addressing learners' individual concerns and differences. This prompted the researcher to conduct the study. It was intended to respond to students' learning needs and to approximate the teachers' instructional method of teaching the subject. Since there are required competencies manifested among students of Araling Panlipunan, the researcher hoped that identifying learning preferences and matching them with teachers' teaching styles could provide the needed boost to attain improved academic performance. Although various interventions to improve the learners' performance have been implemented for years, the dismal figure has remained the same. The result indicates that the needed competencies have not been fully mastered by the learners. At this juncture, the researcher took the challenge of undertaking a study that could provide a roadmap towards a better Araling Panlipunan performance through the identification of the learning styles and teaching styles.

2.0 METHODOLOGY

2.1 Method Used

The researcher used the descriptive research, wherein it is a design which aims to "describe the nature of a situation as it exists at the time of the study and to explore the causes of particular phenomena. The study used a survey questionnaire to gather the data and variables needed.

2.2 Research Environment

The data were collected from three national high schools in Valenzuela City, where the Grade 8 students and their Araling Panlipunan teachers were taken as subject respondents as well. The schools involved in this study were as follows: Bignay National High School, Lawang Bato National High School, and Vicente P. Trinidad National High School.

2.3 Respondents of the Study

The researcher selected three public secondary schools among the 20 public secondary schools in the Division of Valenzuela. The three secondary schools have a total of 1,595 students. However, only Grade 8 student-learners were taken purposively as the subject-respondents of this research. Likewise, it also sought participation from 31 Araling Panlipunan teachers representing each of the three secondary schools.

2.4 Research Instrument

The following data gathering instruments were utilized for data gathering:

The survey questionnaire using the Learning Style Inventory (LSI) was the main data gathering instrument. It is a 30-item survey instrument. The instrument was an adaptation of the Perceptual Learning-Style Preference Questionnaire of Fu Jen Catholic University of Taiwan, and the interpretation was adapted from the Learning Styles Inventory (LSI) provided by the Center for Innovative Teaching Experiences (CITE) to determine the learning style of the Grade 8 students.

Using the scoring guide provided, one's learning style may be identified as visual, auditory, kinesthetic, or tactile. Items in the LSI have been classified accordingly. The scoring key accompanying the instrument determines the styles as the major or minor learning style. To answer the survey, the data was codified with numbers one to five, summed up, and multiplied by two.

The scores may be interpreted as follows: 38-50=major learning style; 225-37 minor learning style, and 0-24 =negligible use.

2.5 Data Gathering

In order to collect the necessary information needed for the study through data gathering instruments, the researcher formally asked permission from the Valenzuela Schools Division Superintendent. 1595The Grade 8 students and their Araling Panlipunan teachers were taken as main respondents. They came from small, medium, and large public secondary schools in the Division of Valenzuela. After permission was granted, the researcher conducted a pilot study and administered the said instrument to 30 comparable samples to validate the question. The Cronbach Alpha was applied and later yielded a .945 score. Since the

instrument was rendered valid and reliable, based on a low reliability score, the researcher then sought permission from the school principals of the target secondary schools to distribute the survey questionnaire. The researcher personally administered the question.

Upon approval of the Principals, the researcher requested an endorsement from the coordinators/head teachers of Araling Panlipunan and requested a schedule as to when the researcher would administer the survey questionnaire to the respondents. Finally, the researcher administered the survey questionnaire and retrieved the same, then encoded the data for analysis and interpretation of results.

2.6 Statistical Treatment

The data gathered were processed by employing the following statistical tools drawn with the use of Statistical Package for Social Science (SPSS) version 20. The data were analyzed and later interpreted for quantitative analysis using the following statistical tools:

1. *Frequency and Percentage.* These were used to answer problems in describing the student-respondents in terms of selected variables like: sex, parents' educational attainment, socio-economic status of the family, and grades in Araling Panlipunan; and for the teacher-respondents: civil status, educational attainment, years of teaching Araling Panlipunan, and attendance at seminars and training related to Araling Panlipunan.
2. *Mean and Standard Deviation.* It was used to determine the average preference and the learning styles, and to determine the homogeneity and heterogeneity of the assessment.
3. *Ranking.* This was used to organize the preferences made by students
4. *Paired t-test.* This was used to analyze the difference between the student-respondents' preferred learning styles and the teacher-respondents' teaching styles.

2.7 Ethical Considerations

The researcher obtained permission from the students before conducting the study. A consent letter was provided to ensure mutual agreement before the study began. The participants were assured that their responses would remain confidential and that the data collected would be used solely for research purposes.

3.0 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This chapter highlights the presentation, analysis, and interpretation of the collected data in this study. In the aim of giving accurate and precise answers to the research questions raised in the first chapter, the discussions are presented as follows:

1. PROFILE OF THE RESPONDENTS

1.1. Profile of the Student – respondents

1.1.1. Sex

The table below presents the distribution of the student respondents in terms of sex.

Table 1. Students' Profile in terms of Sex

Gender	Frequency	Percentage
Male	176	50
Female	177	50
Total	353	100

It can be observed from Table 1 that there are 176 male student respondents, or equivalently 49.86%, while 177, or 50.14% of the total student sample, are female. It is quite evident that there is almost an equal number of male and female students who participated as respondents in this study. This implies that the participants are somehow uniformly distributed when they are grouped according to gender.

1.1.2. Parents' Educational Attainment

Table 2 below reveals the distribution of the student respondents according to the educational attainment of their parents.

Table 2. Students' Profile in terms of Parents' Educational Attainment

Parents' Educational Attainment	Frequency	Percentage
Elementary level	63	18
High School level	180	51
Vocational level	25	7
Tertiary (Collegiate) level	72	2
Post Graduate	13	4
Total	353	100

It can be seen from the table above that 180 or 50.99% of the 353 students who took part in this study have parents who have finished schooling only up to high school level. Also, it is worthwhile to note that a considerable number of students have parents who are college graduates. This is reflected in the frequency of 72, which comprises 20.40% of the sample. This goes to show that most of the parents of the students are capable of giving assistance and guidance to their children in their studies.

1.1.3. Socio-economic status of the family

The family's monthly income of the students was collected and used as a fair basis of their socio-economic status. A summary of the data gathered is shown in Table 3.

Table 3. Students' Profile in terms of Socio-Economic Status

Family Monthly Income	Frequency	Percentage
Below ₱5000	110	31
₱5000-₱10,000	87	25
₱10,001-₱15,000	82	23
₱15,001-₱20,000	51	14
₱20,001 and above	23	7
Total	353	100

Legend:

Classification of Income According to NEDA:

Class A - ₱100,000 – Up

Class B - ₱50,000 - ₱99,000

Upper Class C - ₱30,001- ₱50,000

Broad Class C - ₱15,000-₱30,000

Class D - ₱8,001-15,000

Class E - ₱8,000 below

It can be noted from Table 3 that 110 of the surveyed students belong to families earning less than ₱5,000 a month. This constitutes 31.16% of the sample. Also, 87 or 24.65% of the students have families whose household monthly income ranges from ₱ 5,000 to ₱ 10,000. Moreover, 82 or 23.22% of the students belong to families with a monthly income ranging from ₱10,001 to ₱ 15,000. This implies that, as a whole, a great number of families where the surveyed students belong earn a household income that is less than or equal to that earned by a minimum wage worker in a month.

1.1.4. Grade in Araling Panlipunan

The table below reveals the grades obtained by the students in Araling Panlipunan.

Table 4. Students' Profile in terms of Grade in Araling Panlipunan

Grade Range	Frequency	Percentage
75-79	200	57
80-84	103	29
85-89	50	14
Total	353	100

Legend:

Beginning – 74% and below

Developing – 75-79%

Approaching Proficiency – 80-84%

Proficient – 85-89%

Advanced – 90% and above

It can be noted from Table 4 that 200 or 56.66% of the students obtained grades ranging from 75 to 79. Also, there were 103 students whose grades fell from 80 to 84. Meanwhile, only 50 or 14.16% of the surveyed students got grades within the range 85 to 89. These figures may reflect a fair to satisfactory performance of the students in Araling Panlipunan.

1.2. Profile of the Teacher – respondents

1.2.1. Civil Status

Table 5 below reveals the distribution of the teacher respondents according to their civil status.

Table 5. Teachers’ Profile in Terms of Civil Status

Civil Status	Frequency	Percentage
Single	15	48
Married	16	52
Total	31	100

As indicated in the table above, 16 or 51.6% of the students who took part in this study are married, while 15 or 48.4% are single. This may mean that the teachers are somehow there is balance between the number of teachers when they are grouped according to their civil status.

1.2.2. Educational Attainment

Table 6 shows the profile of the teacher respondents according to their highest educational attainment.

Table 6. Teachers’ Profile in terms of Educational Attainment

Highest Educational Attainment	Frequency	Percentage
Bachelor of Arts/ Bachelor of Science degrees	20	65
Master of Arts/Master of Science degrees	11	35
Total	31	100

As shown in Table 6, there are 20 or 64.5% of the teachers hold a bachelor’s degree as their highest educational attainment. Further, there are only 11 master’s degree holders among the sampled teachers. This comprises 35.5% of the sample. These results show that the Araling Panlipunan teachers have enough content knowledge and skills needed to deliver quality instruction among Junior High School students.

1.2.3. Years of Teaching Araling Panlipunan

The table below shows the profile of the teacher respondents based on their teaching experience.

Table 7. Teachers’ Profile in terms of Years of Teaching in Araling Panlipunan

Years of Experience	Frequency	Percentage
Less than 3 years	10	32
3-5 years	13	42
More than 5 years	8	26
Total	31	100

It can be observed from Table 7 that of the 31 teachers who participated as respondents of this study, 13 have 3 to 5 years of teaching experience. Moreover, 10 of them have been teaching Araling Panlipunan for less than 3 years. Also, only 8 of them are experienced for at least six years. These results may imply that the set of teachers who were surveyed in this study is young professionals who are in the first few years of their teaching career.

1.2.4. Attended seminars and training relevant to Araling Panlipunan

The table below summarizes the profile of the teacher respondents who are grouped according to their attendance at seminars, workshops, or trainings relevant to Araling Panlipunan.

Table 8. Teachers’ Profile in terms of Attendance at Seminars

Frequency of Attendance	Frequency	Percentage
Once a year	24	77
2-3 times a year	2	7
4-5 times a year	5	16
Total	31	100

Table 8 reveals that the majority of the surveyed teachers only attend seminars or trainings once a year. This is supported by the frequency of 24 or equivalently 77.4%. Meanwhile, 2 of them participate in seminars twice or thrice a year. Furthermore, only 5 of them, or 16.1% of the teacher sample, have gone to 4 or 5 seminars or trainings in a year. This result suggests that the Araling Panlipunan teachers lack participation on seminars or trainings where they can acquire ideas on how to improve their teaching styles and grasps up – to – date information regarding social sciences.

2. STUDENTS' LEARNING STYLE PREFERENCE IN ARLING PANLIPUNAN

Table 9 below presents the Learning Style Preference of the students in Araling Panlipunan.

Table 9. Students' Learning Style Preference in Araling Panlipunan

Learning Style	Preference						Overall Mean	Rank	Interpretation
	Major		Minor		Negligible				
	f	%	f	%	f	%			
Visual	214	60.62	134	37.96	5	1.42%	38.07	3	Major Preference
Tactile	153	43.34	192	54.39	8	2.27%	36.14	5	Minor Preference
Kinesthetic	203	57.51	138	39.09	12	3.40%	37.97	4	Minor Preference
Auditory	256	72.52	95	26.91	2	0.57%	39.83	1	Major Preference
Group	153	43.34	171	48.44	29	8.22%	35.67	6	Minor Preference
Individual	212	60.06	131	37.11	10	2.83%	38.37	2	Major Preference

It can be seen from Table 9 that there are 214 students who consider the visual learning style as their major learning preference. Also, 256 students identified themselves as auditory learners. Moreover, 212 prefer to learn and accomplish tasks on their own. These frequencies are supported by the computed overall means of 38.07, 39.83, and 38.37 for visual, auditory, and individual learning styles, respectively. Clearly, these major preferences prevail among the students as a combination of one or more learning styles rather than as a single learning preference. This result implies that students tend to learn best when they see representations such as words or pictures and hear explanations, or by listening to a dialogue or conversation. This also goes to show that students maximize learning when they are allowed to work alone. This allows them to check their own ideas via reflective and deep thinking. Furthermore, considering that these learning styles are their major preferences, it can be said that these learning styles are also their strengths in learning.

On the other hand, kinesthetic, tactile, and group learning styles were found to be minor preferences of the students in learning the concepts in Araling Panlipunan. The computed means for these learning styles were 37.97, 36.14, and 35.67, respectively. This implies that students can still manage to learn during situations or conditions featured in a kinesthetic, tactile, or group learning style, but only to some extent. This is congruent with the statement by no less an expert in learning styles, David Kolb (2006), who stated that learning styles are closely related to cognitive skills. Kolb said that different people prefer different learning styles. The finding is supported further by Parreno (2013), who also explored the learning styles among learners, where the learners differ in their ways of learning and perceiving. Some learners may want to visualize the lesson first before they can really comprehend what they hear. Others want to hear or feel to get through the entire learning process. This may be because teachers could have used varied strategies for different lessons, hence the difference. The students interact differently from what they perceived.

Supporting this speculation was rationalized by Dangwal & Mitra (2005), who mentioned in their study that there is a discrepancy in our perception of our learning style and in others' perception of our learning style. It described learning style as the composite of characteristic cognitive, affective, and physiological factors that serve as relatively stable indicators of how a learner perceives, interacts with, and responds to the learning environment.

Interview with students came up with the reasons behind their preferences; Student 1

Student No. 1." *Para saken mam, mas maganda kung individual kase po ditto mas maiintindihan ko at mauunawaan ko yung gagawin ko kesa naman po groupings. Pano po kung walang cooperation yung iba tapos saken lang po aasa syempre mali naman po yun mas maganda kung ako na lang gagawa at least sariling sikap at higit sa lahat worth it kapag natapos at pag nakakuha ng mataas na marka. At mas natututo ako pag nakikita ko yung itinuturo kasi nabivisualize ko.*"(As for me, performing individually is better since I can very well understand what I am going to do, rather than relying on others, what if they do not cooperate, that they will just rely on me, I think that is not good, of course the outcome is good if I did it myself, its gratifying when I get good mark, I learn more, because visualizing myself of what was taught)

Student 1 disliked the idea of being in a group, as others just loaf and rely on her. The student is expressing her thoughts when she presents her reason for preferring individual performance. She prefers to be appreciated for what she is worth for her own performance. This is similar to that expressed by Student 3 from Bignay High School.

Where he narrated

. Student No. 3. *Mas prefer ko po ang individual kasi nagagawa ko po yung gusto kong gawin o ideya ko lang sa work kasi po sa groupings may mga ibat-ibang ideya na nasusunod (I do prefer to work alone, individually, because I do what I want, it's my idea and I can work on it, rather than working with those having different ideas).*

The student claimed that working individually is good for him because one's own ideas are considered rather than with others who have different ideas that he may not be able to agree with at all. Interviewing with others also gave the same expressed ideas. This means the students confirmed with the findings gathered through the survey.

TEACHERS' TEACHING STYLE IN ARLING PANLIPUNAN

Table 10 presents the teaching styles used by the teacher respondents towards students' learning style preferences.

It can be observed from Table 10 that the majority of the teachers use all of the above teaching styles in teaching Araling Panlipunan with the following frequencies: 22 or 70.97% for visual, 24 or 70.59% for tactile, 26 or 83.87% for kinesthetic, 24 or 70.59% for auditory, 27 or 87.10% for both group and individual. These values are backed up by the calculated overall means, which can all be interpreted as a major teaching preference.

Table 10. Teachers' Teaching Style in Araling Panlipunan

Teaching Style	Preference				Overall Mean	Rank	Interpretation
	Major		Minor				
	f	%	f	%			
Visual	22	70.97%	9	29.03%	40.39	5	Major Preference
Tactile	24	70.59%	7	29.41%	41.48	4	Major Preference
Kinesthetic	26	83.87%	5	16.13%	41.74	2	Major Preference
Auditory	24	70.59%	7	29.41%	40.00	6	Major Preference
Group	27	87.10%	4	12.90%	42.84	1	Major Preference
Individual	27	87.10%	4	12.90%	41.68	3	Major Preference

The table above also indicates that the most commonly adopted teaching style is the "group" while the least used is "auditory". This gives light on the idea that teachers often expose their students to collaborative works and less on actual lecture or discussion.

Perhaps teachers shift from one teaching style to another in classes of different abilities and then use a different one in another, depending on the subject matter or lesson for the day. This phenomenon was pointed out by Akhtar (2010), who cited that the primary focus was the identification of perceptual modality. He went on to state that a basic pedagogical principle proposed that the student should have their initial contact with new material by means of their most effective perception.

Furthermore, the result means that the teachers of Araling Panlipunan strongly use teaching styles that can respond to any learning style preference. This reflects their willingness and hard work towards addressing issues on the mismatch between students' learning styles and teachers' teaching styles.

Supporting the quantitative results and analysis were interviews conducted with teachers. Teacher 1 cited that students prefer to express themselves when they are with groups. And they (teachers) become facilitators of student discussion.

"...only facilitator. Teachers prefer collaborative group work instead of individual work in teaching to give a chance to learners to express themselves in small group discussions through sharing and brainstorming.

Accordingly, teachers believe that the strategies that they have been using for years have helped students to develop interpersonal skills and intrapersonal ability. Teacher 2 stated in agreement with teacher 1 with regard to the use of collaboration, as students could easily adapt and then adjust to situations.

... Teachers prefer collaborative group work to enhance students' creativity and reduce the workload for teachers handling a large class

An interview with Araling Panlipunan teachers from another school Cited that adopting a strategy like group dynamics gave better performance in class among students (Teacher 1) as the strategy helps them gain self-confidence..

"...Group dynamics helps each member to accomplish certain tasks. Having so, less skilled individuals will be able to do their part with the help of some group members. Hence, the group activity helps students gain confidence and be recognized. Group dynamics balance tasks and learning among each other. Students acquire something from their groupmates."

This strategy, adopted by teacher 1, allows each student to express themselves, since they have the support of their classmates in group discussion. Lessons are retained since they took part in the discussion; it works well with the "learning by doing". Students learn to become manipulative with ideas and execute such in a way they could express and be heard works well with them. Teacher 3 shared similarly when she said ...

"Most of my students can come up a good outputs " whenever they are working collaboratively, maybe because they are motivated by group members. Since I noticed that, I never fail to include collaborative group work in my classes."

Experiential learning is the most effective way to practice teaching and learning. Hands-on experience enables students to apply the theories in actual experiments, performances, and presentations. Learning by doing provides effective retention of knowledge learnt.

3. DIFFERENCE BETWEEN STUDENTS' LEARNING STYLE AND TEACHERS' TEACHING STYLE PREFERENCES

In order to determine whether students' learning style matches teachers' teaching style, the existence of a significant difference between these variables was analyzed. The result of this analysis is presented in the table found.

Table 11. Difference between Students' Learning Style and Teachers' Teaching Style Preferences

Variables	Mean	Computed t - t-value	t - critical value	p - value	Decision	Remarks
Learning Style	3.862	4.010	2.002	0.000	Reject H ₀	Significant
Teaching Style	4.135					

The table above shows that the computed overall mean for learning style is 3.862, while that of the teaching style is 4.135. Also, it reveals that the computed t – t-statistic is 4.010 ($p < 0.05$), which is less than the critical t – t-value. Hence, at the 0.05 level of significance, the researcher rejected the null hypothesis and concluded that there is a significant difference between students' learning styles and the teaching styles used by Araling Panlipunan teachers in their respective classrooms.

The result implies that despite teachers' efforts to become responsive to students' learning styles, a mismatch between them persists. Meaning to say, the way students learn best is not the way in which teachers carry out their lessons. This is evident in the major teaching preferences and major learning preferences of the students indicated in Tables 9 and 10. Students prefer auditory, visual, and individual learning styles, while teachers mainly use group, kinesthetic, and individual teaching strategies in delivering instruction. Somehow, this possible mismatch requires concrete suggestions on reinventing classroom instruction in order to suit students' learning styles. Rationalizing the result was aptly explained by Farell (2012), who discussed cognitive style theory to further explain the individual differences of learners. It was based on the idea that individuals process information differently on the basis of either learned or inherent traits. Moreover, the study by Claxton & Murrell (2005) supports that individual students' characteristics and behaviors affect learning.

4.0 SUMMARY, FINDINGS, CONCLUSION, AND RECOMMENDATION

4.1 Summary

This study aimed at determining the learning style preferences of the students in Araling Panlipunan and the teaching styles used by the teachers. Also, it aimed to propose teaching pedagogies that may help in matching learning styles and teaching styles.

This study made use of the descriptive method of research, which involved 353 Grade 8 students of Vicente P. Trinidad National High School, Lawang Bato National High School, and Bignay National High School in the Division of Valenzuela City, and 31 Araling Panlipunan teachers from the same schools. The participants of the study were selected using purposive sampling. An adopted survey questionnaire was used to collect the needed data for this study. Before the data collection, Cronbach's Alpha was applied to validate the questionnaire for reliability and later yielded a .945 score. After all the needed data were gathered, they were treated using SPSS employing frequency, percentage, mean, standard deviation, ranking, and paired t-test. The results were analyzed and interpreted to give answers to the specific problems raised in this study.

4.2 Findings

The following are the findings obtained in this study:

1. Profile of the Study

Of the 353 student respondents, 177 are female and 176 are male. The majority of their parents are high school graduates. Moreover, a large number of the surveyed students belong to a family that earns a household monthly income that is below ₱ 5,000. Also, a considerable number in this sample obtained grades ranging from 75 to 79.

Of the 31 teacher respondents, 15 are single, while 16 are already married. In addition, most of them have a bachelor's degree as their highest educational attainment. Nevertheless, it is worth noting that there are 11 of them who have already finished a master's degree program. Furthermore, most of the teachers surveyed have 3 to 5 years of teaching experience. Also, 24 of them admitted to attending only one seminar or training relevant to Araling Panlipunan each year.

2. Learning Style Preferences

The major learning style preferences of the Grade 8 students are auditory and visual, with individual learning preferences, while their minor preferences are kinesthetic, tactile, and group.

3. The teachers used all six styles covered in this study as their major teaching preference towards students' learning styles. From the most commonly used, these teaching styles are group, kinesthetic, individual, tactile, visual, and auditory.

4. There was a significant difference between the learning style preferences of the Grade 8 students and the teaching styles used by their teachers in the Araling Panlipunan subject.

4.3 Conclusions

Based on the abovementioned findings, the researcher arrived at the following conclusions:

The study explored variables that could provide differing outcomes to the explored topics on learning styles preference among students and teaching styles adopted by teachers in the teaching of Araling Panlipunan. It was found that preferred learning styles did not match those of the teaching styles. The finding supports the hypothesis that significant differences exist, thus strongly affecting student performance. Now it can be said that little attention was given to the learning styles of the students. It could have been a basis for the instructional designs in the subject schools because it provides a means of understanding differences among different learners and how they learn.

Thus, it can be inferred that teaching styles that match the learning styles of students who perform academically. The proposed improved pedagogy would be feasible for schools' efforts for improved performance in Araling Panlipunan.

4.4 Recommendations

In light of the findings and conclusions reached in this study, the following recommendations are offered:

1. It is suggested that the students be aware of the specific situations or conditions under which they can learn best. This is for them to have more organized study habits and learning practices. Letting them know of their learning preferences may eventually contribute to improved performance in Araling Panlipunan.

2. The teachers are recommended to seek professional advancement to keep them abreast with the latest trends in teaching that can help them respond to students' needs, interests, and capabilities, and aid them in further broadening their knowledge on the subject matter. This may be done by pursuing graduate studies aligned with their field of specialization. Also, this may be realized through consistent and active participation in seminars and trainings relevant to Araling Panlipunan. Furthermore, an assessment of students' learning styles is advised to be administered at the beginning of the school year to aid teachers in adjusting their teaching styles.

3. It is also recommended for school heads, program supervisors, and other school administrators to initiate the conduct of training aimed at helping the teachers realign their teaching practices to the present needs and abilities of today's learners.
4. The developers and writers of textbooks or other instructional material may include varied exercises in their work that address issues of learning style differences among classrooms.
5. Parallel studies may be done by future researchers to validate the results of this study. They may include other variables beyond the scope of this researcher. Also, they may create a model of teaching that directly responds to a particular learning style.
6. Based on the outcome of the study, the researcher recommends that the proposed teaching pedagogies may be adopted for a more enriching teaching-learning process.

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